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Suitability and feasibility mapping to assess managed aquifer recharge solutions to cope with groundwater pollution

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Groundwater pollution by emerging contaminants is a major concern for world population because of its toxicity to human health and the environment, and the importance of this source of freshwater for the water supply of cities and agriculture. Its origin is mainly related to human activities: household products (Personal Care Products, detergents, disinfectants), pharmaceuticals, industrial chemicals or agriculture among others. These products are disposed of in the sewage systems and, subsequently in wastewater treatment plants and then, discharged to the environment.

To reduce groundwater pollution there are several solutions that can be applied. The use of managed aquifer recharge (MAR) techniques can be used as a barrier for pollutants to reach the aquifer and, consequently, water supply and dependent ecosystems (wetlands, estuaries, etc.), especially when these techniques are combined with other pre-treatment processes (Mumber *et al.*, 2024¹). Within this framework the HORIZON EU MAR2PROTECT project is working to provide a holistic approach to prevent groundwater contamination from the impacts of climate change and global change, using different innovative technologies, which includes a decision support system (DSS). This DSS will, among others, use spatially distributed data using GIS software to assess the optimal location for two MAR techniques (infiltration ponds and ASR/ASTR -aquifer storage/transfer and recovery-), in terms of the physical (suitability) and technical/economic (feasibility) conditions.

In this work, the results of a methodology for mapping MAR suitability and feasibility areas in several demo sites will be presented. The methodology has been adapted from another EU project (PRIMA AGREEMAR), which took into consideration the most up-to-date methodologies throughout Europe (Martins *et al.*, 2024²). In the MAR2PROTECT project this methodology has been adapted by simplifying and reducing some of the variables trying to find an improved replicability in other countries, so a scalable solution can be implemented in the DSS.

The main outcomes of the adapted methodology show that, although losing some level of detail in the territory (due to a lower resolution of some of the data), logic and coherent suitability and feasibility areas for MAR are detected. In this sense, areas where nice hydraulic properties exist, together with low water availability and high water demand, are going to be more suitable for MAR solutions, as well as those areas where potential pollution can exist (e.g. agricultural areas).

References

- [1] Mumber, T.; Ahrens, L.; Wanner, P. *Managed aquifer recharge as a potential pathway of contaminants of emerging concern into groundwater systems – A systematic review*, *Chemosphere* **2024**, 364 (143030)
- [2] Martins, T.N.; Leitão, T.E.; Oliveira, M.M.; Panagiotou, C.F.; Stefan, C.; Chkirbene, A.; Portela, M.M. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*, **2024**, 26 (101280)